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A MULTI-LAYERED IMAGE WITH ELEMENTS OF A THREE-DIMENSIONAL FORM, AS A WAY OF SELF-EXPRESSION

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Abstract

At the moment, there is a trend for conscious fashion and conscious attitude to the environment, which implies a small number of things in the wardrobe. This trend allows you to make very stylish mixes out of things. Layering is one of the main ways to build catchy, spectacular, interesting and stylish images that are remembered and that you want to look at again and again. The fashion industry is actively moving and will continue to move in the direction of layering in outerwear. Layering is created by using several types of outerwear in one set. Modern fashion and urban life give birth to a new formula of layering - elegant and ostentatious. Layering is a trend in itself, but it can be adapted to other trends of the season.

The analysis of modern fashion trends has been carried out, on the basis of which a multi-layered image with elements of a three-dimensional shape has been created. Consumer preferences are also taken into account. A multi-layered image consists of several elements of clothing. The process of creating the image included the search for a compositional form through geometric shapes, the search for a silhouette, the determination of the length and volume of the product, the elaboration of models, as well as the development of designs that maximally implement the conceived models.

Keywords: multi-layered fashion, outerwear, three-dimensional forms.

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1. INTRODUCTION

At the moment, there is a trend for conscious fashion and conscious attitude to the environment, which implies a small number of things in the wardrobe. This trend allows you to make very stylish mixes out of things. Layering is one of the main ways to build catchy, spectacular, interesting and stylish images that are remembered and that you want to look at again and again. The fashion industry is actively moving and will continue to move in the direction of layering in outerwear. Layering is created by using several types of outerwear in one set. Modern fashion and urban life give birth to a new formula of layering - elegant and ostentatious. Layering is a trend in itself, but it can be adapted to other trends of the season (Elkina, A. P., 2022, 506-508).

Different models of coats from strictly cut to relaxed silhouettes and bright colors will be relevant in the new season 2022-2023. Therefore, the main must-have of autumn-winter outerwear will be a coat of a rich fashionable color. Bright green, yellow, pink, orange, crimson, purple, neon novelties of outerwear can become a colorful accent of the image, or part of a stylish multicolored bow, which can be made only with a clear understanding of the correct combination of colors in the kit.

Especially relevant in newfangled sets will look bright outerwear in the styles of an elongated trench coat, a coat below the knee, a short puffed jacket. As well as a vest, which has again become a trend of the season. The fashion for vests began with stylish knitted vests. Now vests can completely replace outerwear both in autumn and winter. Long quilted vests, trench vests, leather, wool and tweed models of vests are more relevant than ever. In the images, such outerwear is combined with any clothing, both with an office dress code and casual street style (Kiseleva M. V., 2011, 12-16).

The most touching trend of women's fashion is the trend for voluminous sleeves. This item of clothing has been in the trends for more than a year. The trend has not been fixed in the format in which it

originated, it continues to change — this interesting element adorns today not only light summer dresses, tops and shirts, but also weighty knitted sweaters, as well as coats. And, apparently, nothing will change in the near future, because the further away, the more voluminous these sleeves become. In the autumn-winter Fendi collection, a flashlight sleeve with a lowered shoulder line became the main accent of the collection, decorating knitted, velvet and satin dresses, soft mohair cardigans, coats and even fur coats. Alexander McQueen has a similar story — the shoulders are also slightly lowered, and the flashlight complements almost every dress in the collection that has a sleeve at all (Ryzhova Y.I., 2022, 556-557).

2. METHOD

Based on modern trends, an image has been developed that corresponds to the current fashion and consumer needs. The image is based on an elongated vest of the basic design and color of the material. A bolero (Ryzhova Y.I., 2022, 450-455) with unusual structural elements and voluminous sleeves is worn on top of the vest, which is a bright contrasting interchangeable accent of the image.

The 1st stage of image creation is the search for a compositional form through geometric shapes (Fig.1). This stage is necessary to determine the silhouette. The vest is based on: a rectangle, creating a straight silhouette; a triangle, combined with the top, creating an hourglass silhouette and emphasizing the waistline; a trapeze, emphasizing the shoulder line. The bolero is based on a circle and an oval, creating a different volume in the composition of the costume. The third composition was chosen as the main one, as the most harmonious and the most responsive to requests and preferences.

Figure 1 – Composite forms of the costume

The 2nd stage of image creation is the elaboration of models.

The image is based on an elongated vest made of a coat fabric of a solid color of a semi-fitting silhouette, emphasizing the curves of the figure, namely the waistline. With reliefs on the front and back, coming out of the armhole and coming into the bottom line, with a central supate clasp for four swept loops and four buttons, with pockets in the side seams, with a turn-down collar with a cut-off stand and with a flyaway slot (V. V. Getmantseva, 2019, 71-75). The vest is minimalistic, does not contain unnecessary elements, but it is functional, suitable for wear in the autumn-spring period. The technical sketch of the vest is shown in Figure 2.

3. FINDINGS

A bolero made of bright-colored coat fabric is worn over the vest, which makes the image bright, interesting and comfortable. Bolero is an accent element of the image, which can be removed or replaced if desired. The bolero design has articulations coming out of the shoulder seam and coming into the side, which create three-dimensional elements on the mill. The sleeve is one-piece, having a rounded configuration of the middle seam and a curly bottom line. With articulations coming out of the armhole and coming into the bottom line, and vertical pinches at the bottom of the sleeve (V. V. Getmantseva, 2016, 34-57). A technical sketch of the bolero, as well as alternative models of the top, is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2 – Compositional and technical drawing of the images being developed

4. CONCLUSION, DISCUSSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The developed variants of multi-layered images meet modern trends and consumer tastes. Further work consists: in the development of structures that maximally implement the conceived models; in the construction of patterns; in the tailoring of products.

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